

Habitat selection of Greater Hoopoe Lark (*Alaemon alaudipes*), in Bushehr Province

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Received: 22 May 2024 / Revised: 15 July 2024/ Accepted: 19 July 2024 / Published online: 18 September 2024.

How to cite: Ramezani, Z., Shafaeipour, A., Fathinia, B. (2024). Habitat selection of Greater Hoopoe Lark (*Alaemon alaudipes*), in Bushehr Province, Scientific Reports in Life Sciences 5(3), 57-70. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13784492>

Abstract

In this study, which was carried out in the spring of 2022, a total of 20 points including 10 presence (nest) points and 10 absence points of Hoopoe Lark (*Alaemon alaudipes*) were investigated in an area of approximately 2000 hectares, in the vicinity of the Persian Gulf in Bushehr and Tangestan townships, Bushehr province, southern Iran. The characteristics of each nest as well as the environmental characteristics were investigated. The large and small internal nest diameters are 8.1 ± 1.19 and 6.55 ± 1.01 cm, respectively. The average large and small external diameter of the nests is 13.60 ± 1.71 and 11.8 ± 1.47 cm, respectively. The average depth of nests is 4.40 ± 1.07 cm. The average distance from the bottom edge of the nest to the ground surface is 17.3 ± 7.04 centimeters. The volume of the nests was 181 ± 68.08 cubic centimeters. The average distance between nests is 1244.88 ± 665.71 meters. Seven out of 10 nest directions are toward north, two is slightly towards the east and one slightly towards the west. Three environmental variables, including the distance to the asphalt road, the number of short shrubs and the percentage of bare land have significant relationship with the nest points. The nest points have a positive significant relationship with the number of short shrubs and the percentage of bare ground and had an inverse relationship with the distance to the asphalt road. The average height of the bushes on which the nests are built is 48.9 ± 9.31 cm.

Keywords: Bare land, Asphalt Road, Environment, Shrubs

Introduction

The lark family (Alaudidae) belongs to the Passeriformes order, which is a large family of singing birds that includes a total of 97 species in 21 genera. (Mansoori, 2001; Spottiswoode et al., 2013). There are 17 species of this bird in Iran (Kaboli et al., 2016). In terms of current distribution and diversity, larks are primarily an African family and secondarily a Eurasian family. There are 78 species in Africa, 60 of which are native to southern Africa, and Eurasia has 37 species. In most lark species, there is no sexual dimorphism, although males are usually larger than females, and, in some species, the plumage of males and females are very different (De Juana et al., 2004). The Greater Hoopoe Lark *Alaemon alaudipes* belongs to the lark family and in flight, black and white stripes can be seen on its wings, similar to the Hoopoe. This bird is 19 cm long and is one of the larger larks. It has a sandy brown back, a white underbelly, and often black speckles on its chest, as well as a white eyebrow stripe with a narrow black line. Its beak is slightly curved downwards and its wings are long (Mansoori, 2001).

The Greater Hoopoe Lark lives in deserts and semi-desert areas, usually accompanied by low sandy hills, and avoids agricultural lands and foothill areas (Roberts, 1991). This bird inhabits sandy steppes with herbaceous plants, flat salt marshes with scattered plants, seasonal streams with sandy beds, large and small dunes, and abandoned fields. This bird is widespread in Iran, living in the desert basins in the center and lowlands of the south and northeast coasts of the country. It does not have much tendency to fly and only performs beautiful flights consisting of vertical takeoffs and landings during singing or mating displays. It often runs several hundred meters on sand and remains motionless in a crouched position. It is monogamous and its nest is a cup made of thin branches and stems that it builds inside or on top of bushes (Kaboli et al., 2016). In the present study investigating the environmental variables related to the presence and absence of Greater Hoopoe Lark, we have also investigated the nest structure of this bird in Bushehr province.

Material and methods

The study area is the desert regions of Bushehr province located in the cities of Bushehr and Tangestan. Bushehr province is located in the south of Iran on the coast of the Persian Gulf, between 27 degrees and 14 minutes to 30 degrees and 16 minutes north latitude and 50 degrees and 6 minutes to 52 degrees and 58 minutes east longitude. The average elevation above sea level is about 18 m. The climate is warm and humid, with an average annual rainfall of 259 mm and an

average annual temperature of 25 °C. Wind speed varies between 16 to 26 km/hr. The humidity also varies between 43 to 68 percent (Management and Planning Organization of Bushehr Province, 2014). The dominant plant in the study area is halophytic vegetation, specifically *Halocnemum strobilaceum*. The search for the presence of the Greater Hoopoe Lark began in late March by tracking and identifying the approximate areas covering about 2000 hectares through experienced individuals in this field. Since this bird is present in desert areas, a significant part of the search had to be done without a car. To find the location of the nests, almost all suitable areas in the region were investigated. Search activities were carried out two to three times a week in the morning from sunrise until near noon. The first nest was recorded on April 8th, 2022, and 10 nests were recorded by late June. Playback of calls was not used. Since the bird had distinct flight patterns, it was mostly seen with the naked eye, but when walking on the ground, binoculars were needed. After finding the nests, 20x20 meter plots were created to measure the parameters, and all nest characteristics were measured and recorded.

During the study, a total of 10 nests were examined as presence points, and 10 points were examined as absence points. To conduct the surveys, a plot centering around the nest was formed with dimensions of 20 meters by 20 meters. All environmental variables (percentage of bare ground coverage, percentage of rock coverage, percentage of pasture coverage, percentage of cushion plant coverage, number of short shrubs, number of tall shrubs, percentage of livestock presence, percentage of agricultural coverage, percentage of burnt land, percentage of hedge presence, distance to the sea, distance to asphalt road and distance to nearest water source) were investigated. A point was considered as an absence point by distancing from each presence point, and all environmental factors at these points were also calculated with the 20-meter by 20-meter plot in mind. (Diaz, 1994). Of course, it should be noted that the variables of percentage of rock coverage, percentage of pasture coverage, percentage of cushion plant coverage, percentage of livestock presence, percentage of agricultural coverage, percentage of burnt land, and percentage of hedge presence were equal to zero in all places, so they were not considered as predictive variables. All characteristics of nests and bushes (height of the nest from the ground, depth of the nest, vertical and horizontal diameters of the nest, geographical direction of the nest, nest volume, height of the shrub, and distance between the nests) measurement and in the notebook was recorded.

The geographical direction of the nests and the coordinates of the nests were determined using GPS Test software. To calculate the distance between the nests, the distance from the nests to the nearest water source, the distance to the sea, and the distance from the nests to the road were noted, and then the GIS program was used to prepare a map of the nest distribution (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Map of the study area and sampling points

The percentage of bare ground cover was estimated visually. A metal meter was used to measure the height of the nest from the ground, depth of the nest, vertical and horizontal diameters of the nest, height of the shrub. Additionally, the following method was used to calculate the nest volume: the horizontal and vertical radii and depth of the nest were first measured, and then the horizontal radius was multiplied by the vertical radius and by 3.14 (π), and the result was multiplied by the

depth of the nest. It should be mentioned that this formula was used due to the cylindrical shape of the nests. Raw data were analyzed using SPSS software version 23 and Excel version 2010. Initially, the normality of environmental variables was checked using the Shapiro-Wilk test. This test is used to check the normality of data with less than 2000, and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used for data of more than 2000. If the significance level is less than 0.05, the distribution is non-normal, otherwise the distribution is normal. To compare two groups in the case of normal distribution, the parametric independent sample T-test is used, and in the case of non-normal distribution, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test is used.

The relationships between the variables with the points of presence and absence of the nest were investigated using the binary logical regression method and their significance level was calculated. This method is suitable for studies of used and unused habitats by using a random sampling method.

Some methods are used to measure the accuracy of the logical regression model. Among these methods, Hosmer and Lemshow's goodness of fit test is used in this research.

In this test, if the significance level is less than 0.05, the model does not fit well with the data, and if the probability value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning that the model fits the data well (Ebrahimpour & Nowruzzadehrahimi, 2007). A significance level of 0.05 was defined for these statistical tests.

Results

Environmental variables

In this study, the distance of nests from the water source ranged from 791 to 3840 meters, which was between 979 to 3610 meters in areas where the nest was absent. The distance from nests to the asphalt road was between 431 to 1448 meters, and between 780 to 2480 meters where nests were absent. The number of tall shrubs at nest sites was between 1 to 5, and between 8 to 36 where nests were absent. The number of short shrubs at nest sites was between 2 to 13, and between 1 to 7 where nests were absent. The percentage of bare land at the nest site was between 85 to 94%, and between 61 to 91% where nests were absent. The distance of nests from the sea was between 3346 to 4850 meters and between 3460 to 5035 meters where nests were absent (Table 1).

Table 1. Significance test and descriptive statistics of environmental variables (n=10)

Environmental Variables	Points	Mean \pm standard deviation	Range	sig	Test
Distance to the asphalt road (m)	presence	1100 \pm 298.8	431-1448	0.01	T-test
	non-presence	1710.60 \pm 587.95	780-2480		
Distance to water source (m)	presence	1991.6 \pm 877.96	791-3840	0.57	Mann-Whitney U test
	non-presence	1908 \pm 793.26	979-3610		
Number of tall shrubs	presence	2.30 \pm 1.15	1-5	0.001	Mann-Whitney U test
	non-presence	23.80 \pm 8.37	8-36		
Number of short shrubs	presence	6.60 \pm 3.09	2-13	0.003	Mann-Whitney U test
	non-presence	2.80 \pm 1.75	1-7		
Percentage of bare land	presence	91/10 \pm 2.68	85-94	0.001	Mann-Whitney U test
	non-presence	73/40 \pm 9.20	61-91		
Distance to the sea (m)	presence	3916 \pm 497.24	3346-4850	0.796	Mann-Whitney U test
	non-presence	3981 \pm 495.34	3460-5035		

The data were checked for normality or non-normality and the results are shown in Table 2. According to this table, the normal data were entered into the T-test, and the data that were not normal were entered into the Mann-Whitney U test (Table 1).

Table 2. Variable's normality test

Environmental variables	Shapiro-wilk		
	Statistic	Degrees of freedom	Sig
Distance to the asphalt road	0.949	20	0.349
Distance to water source	0.886	20	0.023
Number of tall shrubs	0.830	20	0.002
Number of short shrubs	0.898	20	0/038
Percentage of bare land	0.863	20	0.009
Distance to the sea	0.871	20	0.012

In Table 3, the data has been entered into logistic regression analysis and the type of relationships between the data is shown in this table. The value of Nagelkerke R Square for the variables of distance to the asphalt road, distance to the water source, number of tall shrubs, number of short shrubs, percentage of bare ground coverage, and distance to the sea are equal to 0.42, 0.004, 0.75, 0.53, 0.82 and 0.006 respectively. Which shows that the variable of distance to the asphalt road explains a share of 42%, the variable of the distance to water source explains a share of 0.4%, the variable of the number of tall shrubs explains a share of 75%, the variable of the number of short shrubs explains a share of 53%, the variable of the percentage of bare ground coverage explains a share of 82% and the variable of distance to the sea explains a share of 0.6% of the dependent variable (Table 3).

Table 3. Coefficients of environmental variables of the Logistic Regression model

Environmental Variables	Points of presence and non-presence			
	B	sig	Nagelkerke R Square	-2 Log likelihood
Distance to the asphalt road	-0.003	0.04	0.42	19.98
Distance to water source	0.00	0.81	0.004	27.67
Number of tall shrubs	-10.4	0.99	0.750	0.00
Number of short shrubs	0.716	0.021	0.53	17.56
Percentage of bare land	0.406	0.03	0.82	8.44
Distance to the sea	0.00	0.76	0.006	27.63

Table 4 shows the Hosmer and Lemeshow Goodness of Fit Test for each variable. In this analysis, $p > 0.05$ for all variables.

Table 4. Hosmer and Lemeshow Goodness of Fit Test

Environmental Variables	Points of presence and non-presence		
	Chi-square	Degrees of freedom	Sig
Distance to the asphalt road	9.96	8	0.268
Distance to water source	7.95	8	0.438
Number of tall shrubs	0.00	5	1.00
Number of short shrubs	3.45	6	0.750
Percentage of bare land	3.15	7	0.870
Distance to the sea	1.28	8	0.996

Nests' structure

In this study, the nests were cup-shaped with a shallow oval depression and were made of mud, grass, and dry branches of bushes. The nests were constructed in a way that they were completely concealed. The average volume of the nests was $181 \pm 68.08 \text{ cm}^3$, the average depth of the nests was $4.40 \pm 1.07 \text{ cm}$, the average distance from the ground to the nest was $17.3 \pm 7.04 \text{ cm}$, the average distance of the Distance between nests was $1244.88 \pm 665.71 \text{ m}$ and the average height of the bushes on which the bird had built its nest was $48.90 \pm 9.31 \text{ cm}$ (Table 5).

Table 5. Descriptive statistics of nest variables (n=10)

Variables	Mean \pm standard deviation	Range
Large internal diameter of the nest (cm)	8.1 ± 1.19	6-10
Small inner diameter of the nest (cm)	6.55 ± 1.01	5-8
Large outer diameter of the nest (cm)	13.60 ± 1.71	11-17
Small external diameter of the nest (cm)	11.8 ± 1.47	10-15
Volume of the nest (cm^3)	181 ± 68.08	94.2-274.7
Distance from the nest to the ground (cm)	17.3 ± 7.04	4-27
Vertical depth of the nest (cm)	4.40 ± 1.07	3-6
Distance between nests (m)	1244.88 ± 665.71	100-2900
Height of the bushes (cm)	48.90 ± 9.31	35-65

All nests were built on a plant species called *Halocnemum strobilaceum*, which is a halophytic plant. Seven out of 10 nest directions are toward the north, two are slightly toward the east, and one is slightly towards the west (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The geographical direction of the nests in the studied area

Discussion

The first step in preserving plant and animal species is to have an accurate understanding of their habitats. Habitat selection is one of the main components of ecology and is influenced by both biotic and abiotic factors, which impact the survival of species. Sufficient knowledge of these factors and understanding the most influential ones will assist experts in predicting conservation solutions (Aghanajafi & Ghazanfari, 2018). According to Kaboli et al. (2016), the nest of the Greater Hoopoe Lark is built on a mound of thin branches and stems either inside or on top of short bushes. This indicates a significant correlation between the presence of the bird and the number of short bushes, as the Greater Hoopoe Lark prefers areas with more bushes over those with fewer bushes. Specifically, they prefer shrublands with scattered plants, and the reason for the selection of short bushes could be to create better airflow around the nest and increase nest security from predators like snakes (Kaboli et al., 2016).

According to the present results, Greater Hoopoe Lark prefers bare ground with short shrubs, while other studies conducted on other species of Larks have had different results. For example, Morales and colleagues (2012) found that the presence of the Crested Lark *Galerida cristata* had a negative association with agricultural areas, and Erdos and colleagues (2009) showed that the bird avoided agricultural lands and preferred extensive grasslands for nesting, based on a study of the selection of nesting sites of the Eurasian Skylark *Alauda arvensis* in Hungary. Lameris and colleagues (2009, 2013) compared the selection of habitat of the Black Lark *Melanocorypha yeltoniensis* in natural steppes and abandoned agricultural lands in Kazakhstan and reported that the average population density was three times higher in abandoned agricultural lands than in natural steppes, based on the analysis of 220 nests. Agricultural lands were preferred due to the suitable coverage structure and availability of more food resources. According to Morgado and colleagues (2010), the *Calandra Lark Melanocorypha calandra* is dependent on agricultural lands in their study of habitat selection of this species in wheat fields in Portugal. (Erdos et al., 2009; Morgado et al., 2010; Morales et al., 2012; Lameris et al., 2016). According to Buckingham (2001), the selection of habitat for the Eurasian Skylark in southwestern England similar to our results showed that they prefer bare lands with shorter bushes (Buckingham, 2001). Our results showed that the presence or absence of points at a distance from the water source did not have a significant difference, while the study by Nazemi and Aghanajafi on the Crested Lark in the Marvar protected area in Yazd province showed that the average distance from the nearest water source in nesting sites was less than in non-presence points. Additionally, in this study, contrary to our results, the distance to the asphalt road did not show a significant difference in presence and absence points (Nazemi & Aghanajafi, 2021).

Our results showed that the average height of shrubs containing nests is 48.9 cm, while According to Ali and Riply (1987) and Nadeem et al. (2011), all nests were on average shrubs with a length of more than 60 cm above the ground. (Ali & Riply, 1987; Nadeem et al., 2011). Additionally, According to Birdlife International (2004), the Greater Hoopoe Lark builds nests on the ground (Birdlife International, 2004). Probably, the reason for not building nests on the ground in this area is due to the presence of animals such as dogs, foxes, etc., as nest placement on the shrub provides more cover and they can be safe from predators. Additionally, they can stay away from the heat of the ground in this way. Another possibility is that nests on shrubs are more stable and can withstand severe storms that occur in this area. According to Hartiey (1964) and Shkedy et al. (1992), the

Crested Lark showed that this species builds its nests on the ground, but near vegetation cover to provide warmth and shelter for chicks and eggs in the steppe area. According to Orban et al. (2004), the showed that Crested Lark in Hungary chooses places for nesting that have the most protection against the wind. (Hartley, 1946; Shkedy et al., 1992; Orban et al., 2004). Our results show that the only plant species present in the region is *Halocnemum strobilaceum*, which due to the soil type of the area, which is saline, has a greater growth and its resistance to hot and arid weather has caused it to survive in this region. According to Nadeem et al. (2011), the most used plant species are *Astrogalus stocksii*, *Convolvulus spinosus*, and *Haloxylon griffithii* (Nadeem et al., 2011).

According to Piha et al. (2003), the habitat characteristics of the Eurasian Skylark in southern Finland found that the bird avoids forest edges and its distribution is strongly related to the landscape features of agricultural areas. Vegetation cover and the amount of grass have a positive effect on the density of the Eurasian Skylark, while broad-leaf crops have a negative relationship with its density (Piha et al., 2003). However, according to our results, the Greater Hoopoe Lark has a positive relationship with the percentage of bare land and prefers areas with low vegetation cover. According to Thomsen et al. (2001), the habitat selection of the Eurasian Skylark in New Zealand reported that this species selects open agricultural areas and has a higher density in larger areas, which is inversely related to the height of vegetation cover (Thomsen et al., 2001). According to Garza et al. (2005), the habitat selection in the Dupont's Lark *Chersophilus duponti* in and reported similar results to ours for the Greater Hoopoe Lark that the Dupont's Lark positively selected areas of short shrub cover at ground level and contrary to our report that there was no significant relationship with the number of tall shrubs, Dupont's Lark has an inverse relationship with tall shrubs and avoids areas covered by tall shrubs on the ground. The Dupont's Lark preferred areas with *Genista pumila* but showed less interest in *Genista scorpius* shrubs, dry grass, and cereal crops (Garza et al., 2005).

According to Aghanajafi and Ghazanfari (2018), the nesting habitat selection of the Crested Lark and found that the average number of plant species, including *Zygophyllum*, *Artemisia*, and soil with a somewhat firm texture, was significantly higher in the nesting areas than in other areas. The most influential factors in the habitat selection by this bird were the number of plant species, including *Zygophyllum*, and the type of soil texture, while all the nests of the Greater Hoopoe Lark were made on a halophytic plant *Halocnemum strobilaceum* according to our results (Aghanajafi & Ghazanfari, 2018). According to Ito et al. (2020), the density and habitat selection of the

Eurasian Skylark in the Taruma volcano range in Japan. Similar to our results, these birds also preferred habitats with short vegetation cover. The Eurasian Skylark had its territories in areas where the plant species *Carex oxyandra* and *Arcteryx obtusus* were present (Ito et al., 2020). The study of the effect of habitat characteristics on nest site selection in the Desert Lark *Ammomanes deserti* in southern Iran in 2021, like the present results have shown that the nesting sites have low vegetation cover. They also preferred to choose the margins of large rocks and sometimes small cavities next to the rocks as their nests to protect the nest and its contents from direct sunlight in areas where there is little shade. This is because according to the results of the present study, all the nests were built on the plant bush. Also, contrary to the results of the current research, the direction of most nests was towards the north; in this report, regarding Desert Lark, the direction of most of the nests was towards the east (50%) and south (25%), which is to reduce the effect of direct sunlight and wind (Pakniat et al., 2021).

The study of the habitat selection of two species of small Greater Short-toed Lark *Calandrella rufescens* and Theklae Lark *Galerida theklae* in the bush-steppe regions of Europe, contrary to the results of the present study, showed that these two species build their nests on the ground, but like our report they build the nest in the north or northeast direction, which has been reported to be the reason for the better growth of the mass and body weight of the bird (Yanes et al., 1996).

Based on the studies conducted and the results obtained from the collected data analysis, the Greater Hoopoe Lark builds its nest in flat salt marshes on halophytic plants with an average height of 48.90 ± 9.31 cm, where the three criteria of the number of short shrubs, bare ground percentage, and distance to the asphalt road are important and have a significant relationship with the presence of the bird. According to the analysis, there is a direct relationship between the number of short shrubs and nesting, which means that nesting increases with the increases in the number of short shrubs ($P < 0.05$, $b = 0.716$). It also has a direct relationship with the percentage of bare ground, and as the percentage of bare ground increases, the probability of bird presence also increases ($P < 0.05$, $b = 0.406$). The distance to the asphalt road has an inverse relationship with the presence of this bird ($P < 0.05$, $b = -0.003$).

Conclusion

In this study, 20 points including 10 presence (nest) points and 10 absence points of Hoopoe Lark were investigated in Bushehr province, southern Iran. The characteristics of each nest were investigated. All nests were built on a plant species called *Halocnemum strobilaceum*, which is a halophytic plant. The average height of the bushes on which the nests are built is 48.9 ± 9.31 cm. Environmental variables like distance to the asphalt road, number of short shrubs, and percentage of bare land significantly influenced nest points. The nest points have a positive significant relationship with the number of short shrubs and the percentage of bare ground and had an inverse relationship with the distance to the asphalt road. The study highlighted the importance of the northward orientation of nests for better growth of the bird

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